

Research on Control Rod Cusping Effect Correction Methods Based on NECP-X

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ABSTRACT

The cusping effect is one of the critical challenges that must be addressed in the reactor core physics simulations involving control rod movement. This study investigates methods for correcting the control rod cusping effect based on the NECP-X code, with two improved approaches proposed as follows: First, the conventional both axial and radial homogenization (BARH) method in NECP-X was enhanced. Specifically, axial planes with partial control rod insertion were subdivided into sub-planes, each subjected to independent radial homogenization. The radial leakage term of each sub-plane was then approximated using the leakage terms of its adjacent layers. Second, an Axial-Only Homogenization (AOH) method was developed, building on the material-region-based 2D/1D transport method. This method leverages high-precision axial fine-mesh fluxes from material regions to perform flux-volume-weighted axial homogenization. It initially approximates the radial leakage terms of sub-planes using those of adjacent layers, and further refines these terms via pre-calculated radial leakage correction factors. The proposed cusping effect correction methods were validated using the VERA #4 benchmark and the SPERT 3×3 assembly problem. Results show that, compared with the conventional BARH method, the improved BARH method significantly improves the correction accuracy of the cusping effect and is directly applicable to rod movement simulations for typical commercial PWR control rod clusters. For problems involving large, strong-absorber control rods in the research reactors, the AOH method combined with radial leakage correction achieves the highest accuracy, meeting the precision requirements for correcting the cusping effect in research reactors.

Keywords: control rod cusping effect, 2D/1D transport method, NECP-X

1. INTRODUCTION

In current advanced nuclear reactor systems, including large commercial Pressurized Water Reactors (PWRs) and small research reactors, control rods serve as the primary means of power regulation. In reactor core physics calculations, the "cusping effect" of control rods constitutes one of the critical challenges that must be addressed when simulating control rod movement. Similar to other leading one-step transport codes internationally, the numerical reactor code NECP-X employs a 2D/1D coupled transport method[1]. This approach decomposes the three-dimensional problem into multiple 2D planar problems and 1D problems for coupled transport solution, and the requirement for axial homogeneity within each 2D plane leads to significant errors when a control rod tip lies in a plane.

While the adaptive mesh method can largely mitigate the control rod cusping effect, generating excessively fine meshes tends to degrade the convergence of transport calculations. Moreover, during rod movement and burnup calculations, the adaptive mesh method faces challenges in handling the re-division and merging of burnup regions when mesh partitioning changes. International researchers have carried out extensive studies on cusping effect correction methods for high-fidelity neutronics codes. Bumhee Cho et al. proposed the Neighboring Spectral Index (NSI) method and implemented it in the CRX-2K code [2], which evolved from the Inverse of Spectral Index (ISI) method originally proposed by Yamamoto for 3D pin-by-pin calculations [3]. The nTRACER code employs an

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Approximate Flux Weighting (AFW) method to correct the cusping effect [4]. Aaron Graham et al. applied the collision probability method to address this issue, implementing a Subplane Collision Probabilities (Subplane+CP) method in the MPACT code [5]. However, these existing methods are primarily tailored to typical Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) control rod clusters, which are characterized by small radial dimensions, dispersed core positions, and relatively low differential worth. In contrast, for large-sized, strong-absorber control rods in research reactors, where differential worth is significantly higher and associated cusping effect is more pronounced, systematic correction methods remain largely unexplored.

Based on the original Both Axial and Radial Homogenization (BARH) method in NECP-X, this study investigates an improved BARH approach. To address the cusping effect of large-sized, strong-absorber control rods in research reactors, an Axial-Only Homogenization (AOH) method and a sub-plane radial leakage correction method were developed under the material-region-based 2D/1D transport framework. Subsequent numerical validation and analysis of these methods are presented herein.

2. HOMOGENIZATION METHODS FOR PARTIALLY RODDED LAYERS

2.1. Both Axial and Radial Homogenization (BARH) Method

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the BARH method.

For a partially rodded layer as illustrated in Figure 1, axial homogenization must be performed for the material region $ireg$ where the control rod is inserted. This is done using the axial fine-mesh flux and the material volume as the weighting factors to obtain the homogenized cross-sections for the 2D Method of Characteristics (MOC) calculation:

$$\Sigma_{x,k,ireg} = \frac{\sum_{ifsr \in R} \phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial} h_{k,ifsr} \Sigma_{x,k,ireg}^R + \sum_{ifsr \in UR} \phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial} h_{k,ifsr} \Sigma_{x,k,ireg}^{UR}}{\sum_{ifsr \in R} \phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial} h_{k,ifsr} + \sum_{ifsr \in UR} \phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial} h_{k,ifsr}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial}$ is the neutron flux density of the axial fine-mesh $ifsr$ in material region $ireg$ of layer k , obtained from the 1D SN calculation, $h_{k,ifsr}$ is the height of the axial fine-mesh $ifsr$.

In the conventional 2D/1D coupled transport method, the 1D SN calculation solves the problem for homogenized pins. The axial fine-mesh fluxes obtained by solving the 1D equations correspond to individual pin $ipin$, so it could not directly obtain the axial fine-mesh fluxes for material region $ireg$ required for axial homogenization. To address this limitation, the following assumptions are introduced: the radial flux distribution of the rodded part in layer k is assumed to be identical to that of layer $k+1$, and the radial flux distribution of the unrodded part in layer k is assumed to be identical to that of layer $k-1$. Based on these assumptions, the axial fine-mesh fluxes for the rodded and unrodded parts of material region $ireg$ in layer k can be derived as follows:

$$\phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial,R} = \phi_{k,ifsr,ipin}^{Axial,R} \times \frac{\phi_{k+1,ireg}^{Radial}}{\phi_{k+1,ipin}^{Radial}}, \quad \phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial,UR} = \phi_{k,ifsr,ipin}^{Axial,UR} \times \frac{\phi_{k-1,ireg}^{Radial}}{\phi_{k-1,ipin}^{Radial}}. \quad (2)$$

After axial homogenization, radial homogenization is performed using the radial neutron flux densities of all material regions within pin $ipin$. These flux densities are obtained from the 2D MOC calculation

for layer k . This yields the homogenized cross-sections for the pin, which are used in the subsequent 1D SN calculation:

$$\Sigma_{x,k,ipin} = \frac{\sum_{ireg \in ipin} \phi_{k,ireg}^{Radial} S_{k,ireg} \Sigma_{x,k,ireg}}{\sum_{ireg \in ipin} \phi_{k,ireg}^{Radial} S_{k,ireg}}, \quad (3)$$

where $S_{k,ireg}$ denotes the radial cross-sectional area of material region $ireg$.

2.2. Improved BARH Method

The conventional BARH method involves significant approximations in the one-dimensional calculation. It assumes consistent cross-sections between the rodded and unrodded portions of layer k and directly utilizes the radial leakage term from the 2D MOC calculation of the entire layer k for the 1D solution. This assumes that the radial leakage terms of the rodded and unrodded parts are the same. Consequently, this approach cannot accurately capture the axial effects introduced by the control rod insertion. To address these limitations, the following improved methodology is proposed.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the improved BARH method.

As illustrated in Figure 2, during radial homogenization, the rodded and unrodded portions of layer k are subdivided into two distinct sub-planes. Separate flux-volume-weighted homogenization is then performed for each sub-plane. This utilizes the radial neutron flux densities and volumes of the material regions from layer $k+1$ (for the rodded sub-plane) and layer $k-1$ (for the unrodded sub-plane), respectively, to obtain the homogenized cross-sections for each sub-plane:

$$\Sigma_{x,k,ipin}^R = \frac{\sum_{ireg \in ipin} \phi_{k+1,ireg}^{Radial} S_{k+1,ireg} \Sigma_{x,k,ireg}^R}{\sum_{ireg \in ipin} \phi_{k+1,ireg}^{Radial} S_{k+1,ireg}}, \quad \Sigma_{x,k,ipin}^{UR} = \frac{\sum_{ireg \in ipin} \phi_{k-1,ireg}^{Radial} S_{k-1,ireg} \Sigma_{x,k,ireg}^{UR}}{\sum_{ireg \in ipin} \phi_{k-1,ireg}^{Radial} S_{k-1,ireg}}. \quad (4)$$

Simultaneously, during the subsequent 1D calculation, the radial leakage term for each sub-plane is approximated by the radial leakage term obtained from the 2D MOC calculation of its corresponding adjacent layer:

$$TL_{k,pin}^{Radial,R} = TL_{k+1,pin}^{Radial}, \quad TL_{k,pin}^{Radial,UR} = TL_{k-1,pin}^{Radial}. \quad (5)$$

2.3. Axial-Only Homogenization (AOH) Method

In the original pin-based 2D/1D transport method of NECP-X, radial homogenization is required for each fuel pin prior to performing the 1D SN calculation. Furthermore, this method cannot directly solve for the axial fine-mesh fluxes of every material region within a pin. These limitations introduce significant approximations into the improved BARH method, constraining its accuracy in correcting the cusping effect for problems involving large-sized, strong-absorber control rods with high differential worth. To overcome these shortcomings, a material-region-based 2D/1D transport method is adopted, replacing the pin-based approach. This method utilizes material regions instead of

traditional homogenized rectangular pins as the fundamental coupling units between the 2D MOC and 1D SN calculations.

Consequently, the fundamental forms of the 2D and 1D equations in the material-region-based 2D/1D transport method remain unchanged. However, because material regions can have arbitrary geometries, the method for calculating their radial leakage terms differs from that used for homogenized pins.

For a material region of arbitrary geometry, the calculation principle for the radial leakage term is illustrated in Figure 3. It can be calculated using the incoming and outgoing angular fluxes along all characteristic lines traversing the material region. The formula for the radial leakage term of an arbitrarily shaped material region is[6]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 TL_{g,m,p}^{Radial}(z) &= \frac{1}{S} \int \xi_m \frac{\partial \psi_{g,m}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega_m)}{\partial r} dS \\
 &= \sum_{l=1}^L \frac{\sin(\theta_z) dA}{S_{area}} \int \frac{\partial \psi_{g,m,l}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega_m)}{\partial r} dr \\
 &= \sum_{l=1}^L \frac{\sin(\theta_z) dA}{S_{area}} [\psi_{g,m,l,out}(z) - \psi_{g,m,l,in}(z)],
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where $\psi_{g,m,l,in}(z)$ and $\psi_{g,m,l,out}(z)$ are the incoming and outgoing angular fluxes for the characteristic line l within the computational domain, dA is the width of the characteristic line, S is the area of the material region, L is the total number of characteristic lines passing through the material region, and θ_z is the polar angle component.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of calculation method for radial leakage term of arbitrary geometry.

In this method, the 2D MOC calculation must compute the radial leakage term for each material region. Simultaneously, each material region undergoes an axial 1D SN calculation, thereby increasing the number of units for the 1D solution. This approach avoids the cross-section homogenization approximation within pins and the planar approximation for radial leakage terms. Furthermore, compared to using flat source regions as the fundamental coupling units between 2D MOC and 1D SN calculations, the material-region-based 2D/1D coupled transport method reduces computational memory usage, achieving a better balance between calculation accuracy, memory consumption, and computational efficiency [7].

When employing the material-region-based 2D/1D transport method, radial homogenization for partially rodded layers is unnecessary. Only axial homogenization is performed to obtain the homogenized cross-sections for the material region where the control rod is inserted, which are then used in the 2D MOC calculation. Moreover, since the fundamental unit for the 1D SN calculation is the material region, this method can directly solve for the precise axial fine-mesh flux of the material region within the partially rodded layer, which is used to compute the axially homogenized cross-sections:

$$\Sigma_{x,k,ireg} = \frac{\sum_{ifsr \in R} \phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial} h_{k,ifsr} \Sigma_{x,k,ireg}^R + \sum_{ifsr \in UR} \phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial} h_{k,ifsr} \Sigma_{x,k,ireg}^{UR}}{\sum_{ifsr \in R} \phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial} h_{k,ifsr} + \sum_{ifsr \in UR} \phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial} h_{k,ifsr}}, \tag{7}$$

where $\phi_{k,ifsr,ireg}^{Axial}$ is the neutron flux density of the axial fine-mesh i obtained directly from the 1D SN calculation.

Similar to the procedure in the improved BARH method, the AOH method subdivides layer k of the partially rodded layer into two sub-planes during the 1D calculation. However, each sub-plane directly uses the real macroscopic cross-sections of the corresponding material. Simultaneously, the radial leakage terms for material region $ireg$ in the two sub-planes are approximated to be equal to the radial leakage terms obtained from the 2D MOC calculations of the adjacent layers $k+1$ and $k-1$, respectively:

$$TL_{k,ireg}^{Radial,R} = TL_{k+1,ireg}^{Radial}, \quad TL_{k,ireg}^{Radial,UR} = TL_{k-1,ireg}^{Radial}. \quad (8)$$

2.4. Radial Leakage Term Correction

Approximating the radial leakage terms of the sub-planes in a partially rodded layer directly with those from adjacent layers $k+1$ and $k-1$ is computationally efficient, providing relatively accurate sub-plane radial leakage terms without increasing computational cost. However, for problems with very high control rod differential worth, further correction of these approximated sub-plane radial leakage terms is necessary to enhance accuracy. This paper proposes the following method, which employs pre-calculated correction factors to adjust the sub-plane radial leakage terms.

First, the control rod is positioned such that its tip is at the axial center. Second, calculations are performed for these rod positions using the adaptive mesh method. When the control rod tip is at the axial center of layer k , the adaptive mesh method subdivides this layer into two layers, $k1$ and $k2$, and adds an additional layer at the rod tip. The correction factors for the sub-plane radial leakage terms, applicable when the control rod is partially inserted within layer k , are then approximated as follows:

$$f_{k,ireg}^R = \frac{TL_{k1,ireg}^{Radial}}{TL_{k+1,ireg}^{Radial}}, \quad f_{k,ireg}^{UR} = \frac{TL_{k2,ireg}^{Radial}}{TL_{k-1,ireg}^{Radial}}, \quad (9)$$

where $f_{k,ireg}^R$ and $f_{k,ireg}^{UR}$ are the radial leakage correction factors for the rodded and unrodded sub-planes, respectively.

Using this method, correction factors can be obtained for the sub-plane radial leakage terms for each active core layer where partial rod insertion occurs. These factors are subsequently used to correct the sub-plane leakage terms:

$$TL_{k,ireg}^{Radial,R} = TL_{k+1,ireg}^{Radial} \times f_{k,ireg}^R, \quad TL_{k,ireg}^{Radial,UR} = TL_{k-1,ireg}^{Radial} \times f_{k,ireg}^{UR}. \quad (10)$$

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. VERA #4 Benchmark

The VERA #4 benchmark, a 3×3 PWR assembly array with a central AIC/B₄C control rod cluster[8], was used to validate the improved BARH method for commercial reactor applications. The control rod was withdrawn in 230 steps. Results obtained from the adaptive mesh method served as the reference.

As shown in Figure 4, the improved BARH method demonstrates superior accuracy over the conventional approach. The k-eff deviation of the improved method fluctuates minimally around 0 pcm (max: +4.3 pcm), whereas the conventional method shows large, negative biases (max: -39 pcm). Critically, the RMS deviation of the control rod differential worth is reduced from 7.2 pcm/step (conventional) to 1.2 pcm/step (improved). The enhancement is visually confirmed in the pin power distribution at a high-worth position (step 46, Figure 5), where the improved BARH reduces the maximum local power deviation from -11.85% to 1.33% and the RMS deviation from 3.64% to 0.33%. These results conclusively show that the improved BARH method effectively suppresses the cusping effect in a typical PWR configuration.

Figure 4. The k -eff and control rod differential worth deviation curves of various methods from the adaptive mesh method for the VERA #4 Benchmark.

Figure 5. 3D rod power relative deviation distribution in the partially rodded layer for VERA#4 benchmark (relative to adaptive mesh method).

3.2. SPERT 3×3 Assembly Problem

The SPERT 3×3 assembly problem is simplified from the SPERT research reactor benchmark[9], featuring a large control rod, was used to assess the methods for research reactor applications. The radial and axial geometric layouts are shown in Figure 6. The control rod moves from the bottom to the top of the active core in 50 steps, with a step size of 1.0 cm. All four methods were tested.

The overall accuracy ranking is clear from Table I: AOH + Radial Leakage Correction > AOH > Improved BARH > Conventional BARH. This trend is visually consistent across the keff and differential worth deviation curves (Figure 7). The superiority of the AOH-based methods is most evident in the pin power distribution at rod step 28 (Figure 8), where the AOH method with radial leakage correction reduces the RMS relative power deviation in the partially rodded layer to a negligible 0.09%, outperforming the conventional BARH by over an order of magnitude.

Table I. Accuracy comparison for the SPERT 3×3 problem.

Method	keff Dev.(pcm)		CR Differential Worth Dev. (pcm/step)		Power in Partially Rodded Layer Rel. Dev. (%)	
	Max	RMS	Max	RMS	Max	RMS
Conventional BARH	-219.9	116.4	119.7	54.1	-4.58	1.48
Improved BARH	93.9	54.3	48.8	26.0	1.52	0.48
AOH	69.0	34.8	32.6	17.6	1.10	0.32
AOH + Radial Leakage Corr.	24.8	14.2	29.3	11.6	-0.19	0.09

(a) Radial layout

(b) Axial layout

Figure 6. Geometric schematic diagram of the SPERT 3x3 assembly problem.

(a) K-eff Deviation Curves

(b) Control rod differential worth deviation curves

Figure 7. The k_{eff} and control rod differential worth deviation curves of various methods from the adaptive mesh method for the SPERT 3x3 assembly problem.

(a) Conventional BARH method

(b) Improved BARH method

(c) AOH method

(d) AOH + radial leakage correction method

Figure 8. 3D rod power relative deviation distribution in the partially rodded layer for SPERT 3x3 assembly problem (relative to adaptive mesh method).

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigated control rod cusping effect correction methods based on the NECP-X code, and the proposed methods were validated against the VERA #4 benchmark and the SPERT 3×3 assembly problem. Numerical results demonstrate that compared to the conventional BARH method, the improved BARH method significantly enhances the correction accuracy for the cusping effect and can be directly applied to calculations for typical commercial PWR control rod clusters. For problems involving large-sized, strong-absorber control rods in research reactors, the improved BARH method shows poorer accuracy for this specific problem type, although it still represents a substantial improvement over the conventional method. The AOH method with radial leakage correction achieves the highest accuracy, meeting the precision requirements for correcting the control rod cusping effect in research reactors.

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